

ADVANTAGES OF RAIN IRRIGATION OF CROPS IN GREENHOUSES

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Abstract

Although three-quarters of our planet consists of water, not all of it is usable. Water in oceans and seas cannot be used as drinking water, and a small part of it can be used for other purposes. As a result, there is a permanent shortage of water for drinking or domestic and industrial use. Rainwater harvesting systems are one of the alternative water supply methods that provide environmental and economic benefits compared to traditional water supply methods used in arid and semi-arid climates with water scarcity. This article presents the advantages of this method of watering crops in greenhouses compared to other alternatives.

Keywords. Ichimlik suvi, ekinlarni sug'orish usullari, yomg'irlatib sug'orish usuli, suv tarnovlari, suv yig'ish tanklari, yer osti suvlari, yog'ingarchilik, erroziya.

Аннотация

Хотя наша планета на три четверти состоит из воды, не вся она пригодна для использования. Вода в океанах и морях не может быть использована в качестве питьевой воды, а небольшая ее часть может быть использована для других целей. В результате наблюдается постоянная нехватка воды для питьевых или бытовых и промышленных нужд. Системы сбора дождевой воды являются одним из альтернативных методов водоснабжения, обеспечивающих экологические и экономические преимущества по сравнению с традиционными методами водоснабжения, используемыми в засушливом и полузасушливом климате с дефицитом воды. В данной статье представлены преимущества данного способа полива сельскохозяйственных культур в теплицах по сравнению с другими альтернативами.

Ключевые слова. Питьевая вода, методы орошения сельскохозяйственных культур, метод орошения дождеванием, резервуары для воды, резервуары для сбора воды, подземные воды, осадки, эрозия.

INTRODUCTION

Water harvesting is the collection and storage of surface water flows for various purposes in arid and semi-arid regions where common sources such as rivers or wells are scarce. In addition to providing drinking water to people, animals, and wildlife, water harvesting systems can provide additional water for crop growth. Water resources in semi-arid and arid regions are the most important factors limiting plant growth. Rainwater collected through rain gutters on the roof of the greenhouse can be used for watering and growing plants grown in the greenhouses. At the same time, rain gutters and storage tanks in greenhouses should be large enough to collect rainwater.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

To determine the amount of storage in greenhouses, it is necessary to correctly calculate the water consumption of plants in the greenhouse. The total amount of irrigation water required for growing one plant in an unheated greenhouse in April-September is approximately 568.33 l/m². The results show that 61.49% of the irrigation water required for plants can be met by rainwater harvesting. In addition, 47.74% of the total water needs of plants grown in a heated greenhouse can be met by collecting rainwater. The results show that rainwater harvesting can improve agricultural performance, especially in water-scarce areas..

Rainwater from the roof of a greenhouse, if properly collected and stored, can be used to irrigate plants grown in greenhouses. Therefore, it is necessary to provide storage areas of sufficient size for the collected rainwater. Plants grown in a greenhouse and known for their need for irrigation water can be grown using harvested rainwater. Irrigation is a scarce factor in many regions of the world. Therefore, it is necessary to correctly calculate the water needs of crops and carefully develop irrigation systems. Data on evapotranspiration in the greenhouse are important for successful plant growth, calculating water consumption for irrigation, and collecting and storing rainwater. The future shortage of clean water will be the most important problem of sustainable agriculture in Uzbekistan. Abundance of water in rainy periods and insufficient water for irrigation in dry periods is a water problem encountered in regions with different climatic conditions. During greenhouse cultivation, rainwater falling on the roof of the greenhouse can be collected and stored using water tanks. Greenhouses should have enough rain gutters and tanks to collect rainwater. To determine the storage volume of greenhouses, it is necessary to correctly calculate the water consumption in the greenhouse. Rainwater

harvesting can be an effective alternative water supply solution in areas suffering from severe water scarcity. Recently, this irrigation method has become an important option for water supply in arid and semi-arid regions due to its advantages and economic efficiency. Investigating new potential sources of irrigation can help promote more efficient agricultural activities by reducing the amount of highly polluted irrigation water from expensive public wells, wells, rivers or canals.

Issiqxonalar tomiga o'rnatiladigan tarnov va suv yig'ish tanklari

RESULTS

Using a rainwater harvesting system provides certain benefits to the community. First, rainwater harvesting allows better use of the energy source. It is important to do this because fresh water used to irrigate crops is not easily renewable and it helps to reduce wastage. Rainwater harvesting systems are based on simple technology.

The total cost of their installation and operation is much lower than that of water treatment or pumping systems. Repair requires little time and effort. As a result, a considerable amount of usable water is accumulated even without treatment.

The water collected in the rainwater collection system can also be used as drinking water. For many families and small business organizations, this method helps to significantly reduce their utility bills.

It also reduces soil erosion in a number of areas and allows the land to thrive again. In fact, it can be stored in cisterns for use during periods of low water supply.

Rainwater is free of many chemicals found in groundwater, and it is very convenient for watering greenhouses and garden crops. In fact, it is a great idea

to store large reservoirs of collected water to meet other water needs, including cooking, bathing, toilet flushing, washing clothes and dishes, washing cars, etc.

During the rainy season, rainwater is collected in large storage tanks, which also helps reduce flooding in some geographically low-lying areas. It also helps reduce soil erosion and surface water runoff from pesticides and fertilizers, which cleans up lakes and ponds.

But Rainfall is difficult to predict and at times there may be little or no rainfall, limiting the rainwater supply. In areas with limited rainfall, it is not recommended to rely solely on rainwater for all water needs.

Rainwater harvesting systems require regular maintenance as they can attract rodents, mosquitoes, algae growth, insects and lizards. Without proper maintenance and attention, they can become breeding grounds for many animals.

CONCLUSION

With the increase in the population, the demand for water is constantly increasing. As a result, many residential and industrial enterprises are extracting groundwater to meet their daily needs. This leads to depletion of groundwater, and as a result, in some areas of severe water scarcity, there may not be enough water even to irrigate crops. Therefore, rainwater harvesting is a system that is gaining popularity over time. Areas with high rainfall will benefit the most from this system for irrigating greenhouse crops and will be able to easily distribute water to dry land. However, the best part of the system is its environmental benefits, and nature-conscious farmers and gardeners are increasingly using it.

References:

1. Ahi, Y. and Gültaş, HT. Current techniques and technologies in agricultural water management, Agriculture and Engineering. 1, 2018, 72-76. (in Turkish).
2. Allen, G., Pereira, LS., Raes, D. and Smith, M. Crop evapotranspiration, Guidelines for computing crop water requirements. FAO irrigation and drainage paper No. 56 FAO, Rome
3. Baytorun AN., Greenhouses. Nobel academic publishing. 2016, 415. (in Turkish)
4. Çakmak, B., Yıldırım, M. and Aküzüm, A. Irrigation management in Turkey, problems and solutions, TMMOB 2. Water Policy Conference, 2008, Ankara/Turkey. (in Turkish)
5. Frasier, GW. Harvesting water for agricultural, wildlife, and domestic uses, J. Soil Water Cons. 35, 1980, 125-128.

